

EXPLORERS

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THE GEORGE WASHINGTON UNIVERSITY

WASHINGTON, DC

George Washington University

Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering

Lab for Intelligent Networking and Computing

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George Washington University is a research university consistently ranked as one of the most prestigious universities in the US, and one of the wealthiest in the world. GWU provides access to leading international institutions and multinational corporations.

Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering (ECE) work together to explore solutions that will help: develop photonic computing; create state-of-the-art advances in high-performance computing; improve the reliability of cloud computing; create better sensors to detect harmful biological and chemical agents; create and develop energy-efficient and environmentally friendly magnetic refrigeration systems, among many other efforts

The **Lab for Intelligent Networking and Computing (LINC)**, directed by Prof. Suresh Subramaniam, conducts research in a variety of topics on computing and networking. Current topics of interest include optical networking, data center networking, energy optimization in data centers, cloud and edge computing, and IoT.

READY FOR:

OPEN IDEAS

x1 CHALLENGE

RESEARCHERS

INNOVATORS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 825183.

OPEN IDEAS

PROPOSE YOUR OWN IDEA

Submit openly a disruptive idea based on your line of research, product or service. Attract the interest of this US Node.

FOCUS TECHNOLOGY AREAS

AI

Blockchain

Big Data

IoT

5G

Cybersecurity

Cloud/Edge

KEY APPLICATION SECTORS

IT

CHALLENGE #20 - GWU-ENE-01

→ Energy optimization in data centers

Meet the expectations of this US Node through the technology challenge described below

DESCRIPTION

Decreasing energy consumption in data centers by holistically considering power-saving features in servers and networks and by considering the cooling system.

OBJECTIVES

Enhancing the efficiency of resource allocation to meet the desired computational, New methods for scheduling jobs to servers and low-power management policies for servers and network switches, and new methods for thermal management.

SKILLS REQUIRED

Knowledge of data centers, algorithms, and simulation packages.

